

A Review of Diabetes Prediction Using Machine Learning Techniques

Prachi Patel¹, Prof. Manoj Yadav²

1. M. Tech. Scholar, Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering, School of Engineering, SSSUTMS, Sehore
2. Assistant Professor, Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering, School of Engineering, SSSUTMS, Sehore

Abstract: Diabetic mellitus (DM) is a long-term, chronic metabolic disease. It has an impact on how well the body uses the energy in diet. Heart disease, renal disease, eye disease, nerve damage, and pregnancy difficulties will result from the condition's inadequate management. Physicians can enhance their prognosis, diagnosis, or therapy planning processes with the aid of a classification model. The healthcare industry greatly benefits from big data analytics. Database volume is high in the healthcare sector. With the use of big data analytics, it is possible to examine enormous datasets, uncover hidden patterns and information, gain knowledge from the data, and forecast results appropriately. The accuracy of categorization and prediction in the current method is not very great. In order to better classify diabetes, we have suggested a diabetes prediction model in this study that incorporates regular parameters such as age, insulin, BMI, glucose, and so on, along with a few exogenous factors that are known to cause diabetes. When comparing fresh datasets to existing datasets, classification accuracy is increased. Additionally, a pipeline model for diabetes prediction was implemented with the goal of increasing classification accuracy.

Keywords: Diabetic dataset, Classification, Machine Learning

I. Introduction

The most common disease in the world that doesn't target any one age group is diabetes.[1] Threatening people of all ages increases the concern of medical professionals and governments worldwide. It will need thoughtful consideration and investigation to remove this threat from people's lives. Excess glucose, or sugar, is produced when the human body does not produce enough insulin, as insulin is the primary hormone that controls the amount of sugar in our bodies.[9] The underlying cause of this phenomena, as investigated by medical science, is that the lack of insulin increases the conversion of foods high in carbohydrates into glucose, which builds up in the blood and raises blood sugar levels above normal. Diabetes can cause mortality or damage to blood vessels, heart disease, kidney damage, blindness, and other disorders. Diabetes can be managed with appropriate diet management and consistent exercise, but there is currently no such long-term treatment available in medicine [1].

Early and proactive diabetes detection is critical for improved treatment and prevention. Thanks to the researchers' persistent efforts and understanding, multiple diabetes diagnosis approaches have been established. Numerous Neural Network approaches have been applied to diabetes diagnosis to assist medical professionals. Principal element Associate in Nursingalysis and reconciling Neuro Fuzzy reasoning System (ANFIS) is an unusual method that Polat and Gunes use. First, PCA narrows down the options for greater accuracy; second, ANFIS is used to classify the knowledge set on polygenic disorders [4]. In the second step, LDA is also used to reduce the features associated with knowledge of polygenic disorders, with ANFIS categorization [3]. Manjeevan Seera et al. designed three approaches: the Random Forest Model (RF), the Classification and Regression Tree (CART), and the Fuzzy Min-Max Neural

Network (FMM) for use on three distinct medical datasets: Liver Disorders, Polygenic Disorder in Pima Indians, and Carcinoma Wisconsin. When compared to FMM and FMM-CART findings, FMM-CART-RF produces better outcomes. The idea of fuzzy modeling has been successfully applied to diagnostic systems. Three strategies—fuzzy k-nearest neighbor rule, fuzzy clustering-based modeling, and reconciling Network-based Fuzzy reasoning System (ANFIS)—were used to the Wisconsin cancer and Pima Indians polygenic disorder datasets as part of the work designed by Sean N. Ghazavi et al. The achieved classification accuracy is 97.17% and 77.65%, respectively. Polygenic disorder prediction uses multiple approaches, such as C4.5 rule and k-means agglomeration. Pattern extraction uses K-means agglomeration enforced by the Maori Hen tool. The final output is sent into the C4.5 call tree, which is utilized for classification exploitation. To divide the samples into entirely distinct categories, k-fold cross validation is applied. Knowledge preprocessing, which is accomplished via principal element analysis, is extremely important for improving accuracy and scaling the data in the same range of values. By using k-fold cross validation and feed forward higher order neural network exploitation, the classification of the resulting knowledge is finished. Encouragement The field of diagnosis has seen remarkable progress with Vector Machines. SVM classifier with RBF kernel for polygenic disorder knowledge exploitation has been classified in the work planned by V. Anuja Kumari et al. The obtained classification accuracy is seventy-eight. Distribution of cases from a given domain, defined by a set of unique price attributes, into a set of categories—which may be considered values of a chosen set of unique target attributes known as target conception—represents the classification job. Although the correct category labels are usually unknown, they are given for a subset of the domain. It is common practice to generate an instance from the same domain, described by the

same set of characteristics. This is in line with the general premise of inductive learning, which holds that the most prevalent mental representation for the categorization job[2].

The classification approaches are used to help with nosology functions since they assign a category to a variety of knowledge records with particular attributes and their values. A classification model, such as a clinical measurement model, takes in a set of related attribute values and outputs a category of knowledge records.

In this work, we introduce a novel approach to categorize the Pima Indians polygenic disease dataset from the UCI machine learning repository using a Particle Swarm Improvement Neural Network (PSO) in conjunction with multilayer neural networks. The fundamental idea behind this rule is to use PSO to speed up coaching after first determining the optimal PSO parameter by randomly selecting tuples from the input dataset. The searching strategy is changed to gradient downhill looking based on heuristic knowledge if the fitness operate price has not changed for a few generations. In the end, PSO and neural networks are used to classify data into two groups: '0' for negative (not diabetic) and '1' for positive (diabetic).

II. Literature Review

According to this research [1], diabetes is one of the deadliest and most chronic diseases that raises blood sugar levels. If diabetes is left undiagnosed and untreated, several entanglements arise. A patient is seen by a symptomatic focus and counseling professional as a result of the tedious distinguishing measure. But the advancement of AI techniques addresses this fundamental problem. The goal of this study is to develop a model that can most accurately represent the likelihood that a patient would develop diabetes. In order to detect diabetes at an early stage, this research uses three AI characterisation computations, namely Decision Tree, SVM, and Naive Bayes. The Pima Indians Diabetes Database (PIDD), which comes from the UCI AI repository, is the subject of analyses.

The displays of the three separate computations are evaluated using various metrics, including F-Measure, Precision, Accuracy, and Recall. The estimation of exactness is done over both correctly and incorrectly sorted cases. The obtained results demonstrate that Naive Bayes beats with the highest level of precision (76.30%) compared to other computations. These results are verified in a reasonable and systematic manner using Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) bending. Several AI techniques are applied in this study [2] to conduct predictive analysis on massive amounts of data across several domains. Although it can be a challenging task, vision screening in medical services can assist professionals in making highly informed decisions on the treatment and well-being of their patients. This study discusses the future research in healthcare; six different AI computations are used in this analysis. Six unique AI computations are applied to a dataset consisting of patient clinical records in order to analyze the data. The accuracy and efficiency of the used computations are assessed. The correlation between the various AI techniques applied in this analysis reveals the best suitable calculation for diabetes prediction. The purpose of this research is to provide experts and specialists in diabetes early detection using AI methodologies.

This research [3] views the extraction of complicated head and hand developments coupled with their continuously changing shapes as a problematic problem in PC vision for gesture-based communication acknowledgment. This paper suggests using

convolutional neural networks (CNN), an amazing artificial intelligence tool, to recognize Indian sign language through gestures. The technique used in this work is a self-portrait type of continuous gesture-based communication video, where a conference-weakened person can freely operate the SLR flexible application. Due to non-availability of datasets on portable selfie communication using signing, we began by creating a dataset consisting of five different participants who completed 200 signs at five different survey locations with varying baseline circumstances. In a video, each sign featured 60 edges or images. Three unique example estimates are used for CNN preparation; each estimate has a different subject and survey point layout. The two remaining examples are used to test the CNN that has been prepared. In order to improve recognition accuracy, unique CNN models were designed and tested using our selfie gesture-based communication data. Comparing our 92.88% recognition rate to other classifier models published on the same dataset, we achieved a higher accuracy.

According to this research [4], the remarkable developments in biotechnology and wellness sciences have led to the essential creation of data, such as clinical data and high throughput genetic data generated from massive Electronic Health Records (EHRs). In order to turn any available data into meaningful knowledge, biosciences are now more than ever in need of applying artificial intelligence (AI) and information mining techniques. The metabolic problems that accompany diabetes mellitus (DM) place a great deal of strain on people's well-being worldwide. Vast research in every aspect of diabetes (etiopathophysiology, treatment, diagnosis, and so forth) has led to an era of enormous amounts of data. With the main class having all the makings of the most well-known, the purpose of the current examination is to conduct a methodical survey of the uses of artificial intelligence (AI), information mining strategies, and instruments in the field of diabetes research regarding a) Prediction and Diagnosis, b) Diabetic Complications, c) Genetic Background and Environment, and e) Health Care and Management. A wide range of AI computations were used. Typically, 15% of the ones used were by lone learners, while affiliation rules were used to illustrate 85% of directed learning draws. SVM, or backing vector machines, are the most effective and widely used computation. Clinical datasets were the information type that was used most frequently. The titles of the selected papers suggest that it is convenient to omit crucial details, which has led to new theories concentrating on deeper organization and more research in DM.

The goal of this paper [16] is to employ machine learning algorithms to predict type 2 diabetes. The goal of the project is to use a variety of health-related indicators to create a model that can precisely identify people who are at risk of getting type 2 diabetes. The writers use a variety of machine learning methods, such as neural networks, decision trees, random forests, and support vector machines. Metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC) are used to assess how well these algorithms function. The study comes to the conclusion that machine learning models—especially ensemble approaches like random forests—show excellent predictive power and can be very helpful in type 2 diabetes early diagnosis and preventive measures.

The study [20] investigates diabetic mellitus diagnosis and prognosis techniques. In order to improve the precision and effectiveness of diabetes prediction models, the authors emphasize the significance of applying different machine learning algorithms and data pretreatment approaches. The study

offers a thorough method for managing and examining medical data in order to enhance the quality of diagnoses.

Table 1: Summary of Literature Review

Ref. No.	Title, year	Author Name	Methodology	Results
1.	Prediction of Diabetes using Machine Learning Classification Algorithms,, IEEE 2020	Naveen Kishore G, K. Sumedh, T. Rajesh,	Prediction of Diabetes using Random Forest	Accuracy = 74.4%, Misclassification = 25.50%
2.	Prediction of Diabetes Using Machine Learning Algorithms in Healthcare, IEEE 2019	Muhammad Azeem Sarwar, Nasir Kamal, Ali Shah	Prediction of Diabetes using support vector machine	Accuracy = 73.8%, Misclassification = 26.20%
3.	Deep convolutional neural networks for sign language recognition, IEEE 2018	Rao G.A., Syamala K., Kishore P.V.V., Sastry A.S.C.S.	Prediction of Diabetes using deep convolutional neural networks	Accuracy = 72.02%, Misclassification = 27.98%
4.	Predicting Diabetes Mellitus With Machine Learning Techniques, IEEE 2018	Quan Zou, Kaiyang Qu	Prediction of Diabetes using decision tree	Accuracy = 71.46%, Misclassification = 28.54%

III. Proposed Work

The following are the novel approaches we have used in our research: The diabetes dataset is fed into the Hybrid PSO-Neural Network in the Hybrid PSO-NN algorithm. It has nine attributes total—768 samples and one final attribute called "class," which denotes whether an attribute is positive or negative. In this rule, the process of looking out also begins with the initialization of a group of random particles. To find the global best position within the answer region, new particles must first be formed and all existing particles must be updated until a replacement generation set of particles is created. Lastly, the global optimum is searched using the Neural Network rule. In this way, this hybrid rule may detect an Associate in Nursing's peak very rapidly. The following summarizes the process for this hybrid PSO-Neural Network:

Algorithm:

Using the dataset as input for classification, Step 1 of the study involves diagnosing the sickness and initializing the locations and velocities of a group of randomly distributed particles throughout the interval [0,1] along with

various parameter values. Step 2: Determine the fitness value of each initialized particle. P_b is ready due to the present particle positions, while P_g is ready due to the optimal initialized particle position. Step 3: Visit Steps Six and Four if the most numerous generations have arrived.

Step 4: Hold on is the current particle that is the most effective. After updating each particle's position and velocity, a group of the most recent particles is created. If a new particle files on the far side of the boundary [X_{min} , X_{max}], the new position will be set to X_{min} or X_{max} ; if a new rate files on the far side of the boundary [V_{min} , V_{max}], the new rate will be set to V_{min} or V_{max} .

Step 5: Determine each new particle's fitness value; as a result, the best particle is retained and the worst particle is swapped out. In the event that P_{ib} is less healthy than the i th particle in its new location, P_{ib} is prepared due to the i th particle's new location. P_g is updated if the optimal placement of every new particle is healthier than P_g .

Step 6: Apply the best parameter values discovered by PSO in the feed forward neural network to determine the classification rate at the tip.

IV. Classification Methodology

The Hybrid PSO-Neural Network approach, which we apply and compare the experimental outcomes of two techniques—Particle Swarm Optimization and Feed Forward Neural Network combination—for the classification of diabetes dataset is described in our study [15]. 500 data samples are used to train the hybrid PSO NN classifier, and 268 samples are used for testing [16]. Our training and testing results showed a 76.0417% classification accuracy.

Optimization of Particle Swarm:-The following notation is used in particle swarm optimization: X_{id} : A component of the i th particle in dimension d
 V_{id} : The particle velocity of particle I in dimension d
 P_{Bi} : particle I 's best-yet position
 GB : The top spot in the world
 Constant weight factors C_1 , C_2
 W : The inertia weight
 r_1 , r_2 : Random variables in the interval [0,1]
 V_{min} : The particle's minimum velocity, or V_{max} : The particle y_i 's maximum velocity value is: The particle I fitness value

PSO is a population base stochastic optimization method that aims to achieve specific goals using swarm social behavior—such as fish schooling or bird flocking—by securing a favorable location. The PSO method uses a population of potential solutions, or particles, known as swarms. Every particle in a population has a position, a fitness value calculated from a fitness function, and moves depending on an updated velocity determined by a few basic formulas. The best known positions of the swarm as a whole and each individual particle in the search space serve as guidelines for the particles' movements. Each particle's position vector and velocity vector control how the particles move. The vector and velocity vector of the i th particle position in the n -dimensional space are denoted, respectively, as $X_i=[x_{i1},x_{i2},x_{i3},x_{i4},\dots,x_{in}]$ and $V_i=[v_{i1},v_{i2},\dots,v_{in}]$, where x_{id} is a binary bit and $i=1,2,\dots,m$ (m is the number of particles). The neighborhood's prior best performance position is recorded as $GB_i=[gb_{i1}, gb_{i2},\dots, gb_{in}]$.

Equations (A1) and (A2), respectively, serve as the basis for the updated particle position and velocity. With $d=1,2 \dots \text{ely } D$, $V_{idnew} = w \times v_{idold} + c1r1(p_{bidold} - x_{idold}) + c2r2(g_{bdold} - x_{idold})$ (A1)

$X_{idnew} = x_{idold} + v_{idnew}$, $d=1,2,\dots,\text{ely } N$ (A2)

The positive constant values $c1$ and $c2$, which range from 0 to 4, represent the cognitive and social learning elements, respectively. The values of $r1$ and $r2$ are uniformly distributed with integers between 0 and 1, while the inertia weight (w) has a value between 0.4 and 0.9. N is the size of the swarms, and the velocity values fall between v_{min} and v_{max} . 2. Neural Network with Feed Forward Back Propagation Predictive models that can learn, analyze, organize data, and forecast test results in line with it are called neural networks. Among the various types of neural networks, feed forward neural networks are typically used in applications such as medical diagnostics.

These networks are trained using a predetermined set of patterns known as the training set. In our work, Feed Forward NN is composed of an input layer, a hidden layer, and an output layer. The data flows in a forward manner, and errors are minimized by backpropagating the mistakes to update the weights at each epoch. The following two systems, which are explained in 1 and 2, are implemented by neural networks and satisfy the following requirements, as indicated in the suggested work.

epoch count set to 500

There are 15 secret layers.

There are 5 neurons in the buried layer.

Sigmoidal function equals activation function.

Feed forward is the training algorithm. Network Neural

V. Conclusion

Diabetes is a metabolic illness brought on by an elevated blood glucose level. Patients with diabetes do not have enough insulin in their bodies to control blood sugar levels. Diabetes also contributes to a number of other disorders, all of which are harmful to health. Early detection of such a major health risk is imperative. Numerous disorders in the human body are caused by diabetes. Several strategies have been used to help doctors diagnose diabetes more easily. A chosen classification system is evaluated with the diabetic data set.

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